

Sensitive microspectrophotometric determination of thorium(IV) and uranium(VI) with pyrogallol red in presence of cationic surfactant

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Abstract : Formation of water soluble deeply colored ternary complexes of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} metal ions with pyrogallol red (PGR) in presence of cationic surfactant cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide (CDMEAB) have been observed. CDMEAB sensitize the color reactions of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with pyrogallol red with enhancement in molar absorptivities and sensitivities at the shifted wavelength of ternary complexes with stoichiometric composition 1 : 2 : 4 (M-PGR-CDMEAB) have been observed for both the metal ions. The ternary complexes of thorium(IV) at pH 4.0 and uranium(VI) at pH 7.0 exhibit absorption maxima at 660 and 650 nm with molar absorptivities 61120 and 52470 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻² respectively. Beer's law were obeyed in concentration range 0.23–3.24 ppm for Th^{IV} and 0.27–3.51 ppm for U^{VI} in presence of CDMEAB. Conditional formation constants and various analytical parameters have been evaluated and compared the results of newly formed ternary complexes with binary complexes reported earlier. Enhancement in the molar absorptivities in presence of CDMEAB clearly indicated the usefulness of these colored reactions for microdetermination.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, pyrogallol red (PGR), cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide (CDMEAB), thorium (Th), uranium (U), ternary complexes.

Introduction

It is no surprise that the number of methods for determination of thorium(IV) and uranium(VI) is large in view of increased use in the production of energy in a nuclear reactor during recent decades. As thorium has some inherent limitations in the fuel cycle in nuclear reactor, it has not been used extensively as power reactor fuel which ultimately operates on U²³³. While majority of methods report in terms of uranium and a limited number report as uranyl (UO₂) ion which contains 88% uranium.

In early 70's some reactions were reported in which the addition of surfactants decreased the color intensity of organic dyes considerably. Subsequent developments demonstrated that the addition of specific metal ions to these decolorized indicators (dye : surfactant complex) resulted in intense, water soluble, highly colored complex with greater molar absorptivity and solubility than the complex formed in the absence of surfactant and thus

making these decolorized dyes suitable for the spectrophotometric determination of metal ions at low concentration which can not be determined. The increased sensitization of color reactions of metal ions is of great help in analytical chemistry. The greater stability and absorptivity of these complexes becomes a useful tool in quantitative microanalysis of several metal ions as discussed below.

Both pyrogallol red and bromopyrogallol red have been studied in presence of surfactants (CPB and OP-7) by using new optical methods for the determination of Mo^{VI} 1,2, W^{VI} 1,4, Cu^{II} 3, Ti^{IV} 3 and V^V 4 by Ivanov and coworkers. Spectrophotometric determination of Sc^{III} in monazite after separation in presence of reagent eriochrome cyanine R and surfactant CTAB have been reported by Chan-il-Park and coworkers⁵. Determination of Th^{IV}, La^{III} and Y^{III} in some geological and environmental samples have been determined spectrophotometrically by Abdullah

*et al.*⁶. Application of chrome azurol S and benzyldodecyl-dimethylammonium bromide for Ga^{III} determination in mineral fertilizers have been studied by Buhl Franciszek and coworkers⁷. Sm^{III} has been determined spectrophotometrically with chrome azurol S in presence of cetylpyridinium chloride⁸ and some rare earth elements in presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and Triton X-100 by Preisler *et al.*⁹.

Eriochrome cyanine R has been used in selective and sensitive spectrophotometric determination of submicromolar amounts of Al^{III} ion in presence of DTAB¹⁰. A 1 : 1 : 2 ternary complex of neodymium-gallein-cetrimide at 622 nm have been reported¹¹. Ce^{III} has been determined spectrophotometrically with some triphenyl formazan derivative in presence of CPB by Ahmad¹². Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were determined spectrophotometrically with 2-(5-bromo-2-pyridylazo)-5-diethylamino-phenol in presence of cetylpyridinium chloride by Agnihotri¹³ and with diphenylcarbazone in presence of Triton X-100 by Kaur *et al.*¹⁵. A simple spectrophotometric determination of Cd^{II} using 1,5-diphenylthiocarbazone in presence of CTAB has been studied by Khan and coworkers¹⁴. Spectrophotometric determination of V^V in presence of 5-chloro-8-hydroxy-7-iodoquinoline under acidic condition using Triton X-100 as surfactant has been studied by Sharma and coworkers¹⁶. Determination of Cd^{II} with 5-Br-PADAP in presence of CPC and HDPBA have been reported¹⁷. Spectrophotometric determination of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ru^{II} and Mo^{VI} using sodium isoamylxanthate in presence of surfactants like sodium lauryl sulphate, Triton X-100 and CTAB has been reported by Malik and coworkers¹⁸. Micellanized spectrophotometric method for the determination of Be^{II} using haematoxylin in presence of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide has been reported¹⁹.

Most of the reported spectrophotometric methods found to have some limitations for its determination at low concentration and are applicable only at high concentration of thorium and uranium metal ions. Various reagents have been reported for spectrophotometric determination of these metal ions as binary complexes however, most of them lack in sensitivity to the extent of their determination when present in very small concentration. Considerable interest has been developed in last few decades for

the determination of trace amount of thorium and uranium in environmental sites of energy production in nuclear reactor. This initiated the present investigation for development of simple, convenient and reliable method for microdetermination.

Spectrophotometric determination of U^{VI} has been carried out in presence of CTAB by Kant²⁰ and with pyrocatechol violet in presence of CTMAB by Chan-il-Park²¹. Th^{IV} has been determined spectrophotometrically with disodium salts of 2-(2-hydroxy-3,6-disulpho-1-naphthylazo)-benzenearsonic acid (thorin) as a chromogenic reagent by Khan²². Spectrophotometric and complexometric method has been put forth by Khalifa and coworkers for the determination of Th^{IV} and fluoride using bromocresol orange in presence of CPB²³. Amin *et al.* reported simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of Th^{IV} and some rare earth metals with pyrimidine azo dyes and cetylpyridinium chloride²⁴. Simultaneous derivative spectrophotometric determination of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} in micellar medium have been studied by Agnihotri and coworkers²⁵. Microspectrophotometric determination of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} with methyl thymol blue in presence of CTAB have been reported earlier in our laboratory by Upase and Zade²⁶.

Very little work as discussed above has been reported for microspectrophotometric determination of thorium and uranium as ternary or mixed ligand complexes hence, the present study has been planned to suggest really simple and reasonably good method for determination of these metal ions at low concentration, using the reported reagent pyrogallol red (PGR) as a binary complex and sensitizing the reagent with cationic surfactant (CDMEAB) as ternary complexes using spectrophotometer which is still frequently used because of its low cost and simplicity.

Experimental

Instrumentation and reagent solutions :

The spectrophotometer Hitachi U 2001 with matched quartz cell of 1.0 cm thickness was used for all absorbance measurements. Spectral studies were carried out by using deionised distilled water as a reference solution. The pH values of these solutions were adjusted using Elico LI-10 pH meter, operated on 220 volts stabilizer with AC mains with glass and calomel electrodes assem-

bly. The pH scale was standardized and frequently checked with potassium hydrogen phthalate solution of pH 4.02 and borax solution of pH 9.20. For pH adjustment analytical grade hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions of suitable concentration were used. Thorium nitrate and uranyl acetate of analytical grade purity were supplied by British Drug House Company, England. Stock solutions of PGR, CDMEAB and metal ions were prepared of strength $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ and subsequently diluted to desired concentration using double distilled water. Pyrogallol red (PGR) and cetyldimethylethylammonium bromide (CDMEAB), were supplied by Sigma and Aldrich Chemical Company, USA respectively. Purity of CDMEAB was estimated by using argentometric titration for the determination of bromide ion content²⁷.

General procedure :

The CDMEAB solution was first added to PGR solution and kept for equilibration for half an hour. Metal ion solution was then added to dye surfactant solution and again kept for half an hour to reach complete equilibrium. This order of mixing the solutions was maintained throughout the investigation. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature of 30 ± 2 °C.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra :

Effect of pH on absorption spectra of PGR in absence and presence of CDMEAB was studied in the pH range 1.0–12.0 and shows different wavelength of maximum absorbance at different pH values as recorded in Table 1. Values show that λ_{\max} of PGR shifts towards higher side as the pH increases in the range 1.0–7.0 from 480–560 nm showing a bathochromic shift and remains constant at

Table 1. λ_{\max} of PGR in absence and presence of CDMEAB

PGR		PGR + CDMEAB	
pH	λ_{\max} (nm)	pH	λ_{\max} (nm)
1.0–3.5	480	1.0–3.0	480
4.0–5.0	510	3.5–5.0	550
5.5	550	4.0–5.30	580
6.0–7.0	560	4.5–5.0	550
8.0–12.0	450	5.5–7.0	580
		8.0–60	
		9.0–10.0	410
		11.0–12.0	560

450 nm in the pH range 8–12. Notable bathochromic shifts were also observed in pH range 1.0–8.0 in presence of CDMEAB. At pH 9.0 and 10.0 where λ_{\max} of PGR is observed at 450 nm indicates a considerable hypsochromic shift with λ_{\max} of 410 nm in presence of CDMEAB. However in pH range 11.0–12.0 peak appears at 560 nm in presence of CDMEAB. Variations in absorbance maximum could be interpreted in terms of increasing dissociation of protons from PGR in presence of CDMEAB. These spectral changes indicate an early dissociation of proton in presence of CDMEAB which takes place as expected theoretically and indicates the ionic interaction between anionic PGR and cationic CDMEAB. This ionic interaction results into decrease in pKa values with decreased absorbance values as reported in the literature.

Composition of PGR-surfactant complex :

Effect of varying CDMEAB concentration on absorbance of PGR at pH 6.0 at 660 nm as shown in Fig. 1. The four different concentrations of PGR solution were used for curve A - $2.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, curve B - $1.6 \times 10^{-5} M$, curve C - $1.2 \times 10^{-5} M$ and curve D - $0.8 \times 10^{-5} M$. Curves thus obtained by plotting absorbance against CDMEAB concentration show successive decrease in absorbance values of PGR upto certain point where PGR : CDMEAB ratio of 1 : 2 was reached. Almost full decolo-

Fig. 1. Effect of [CDMEAB] on PGR in acidic medium at pH 6.0, λ_{\max} 660 nm.

rising effect was observed at this minimal ratio. Similar results have been obtained at pH 4.0 at 660 nm and pH 7.0 at 650 nm where the further studies of the ternary complexes have been carried out. The absorbance of PGR remains constant even further addition of five times excess of CDMEAB. It may therefore be concluded that association of anionic PGR with cationic CDMEAB thus formed with composition [PGR(CDMEAB)₂].

Effect of mineral salt :

The effect of various mineral salts on the absorption spectrum of PGR in presence of CDMEAB was studied at pH 4.0 at 660 nm and also at pH 7.0 at 650 nm where the further studies of ternary complexation have been carried out. The curves A, B, C, D, E and F in Fig. 2 are for NaCl, KCl, NH₄Cl, KNO₃, NH₄NO₃ and Na₂SO₄ respectively. The chlorides except NH₄Cl have less effect on the absorbance of PGR-CDMEAB complex. The

Fig. 2. Effect of mineral salts on PGR at pH 6.0, λ_{max} 660 nm, A - NaCl, B - KCl, C - NH₄Cl, D - KNO₃, E - NH₄NO₃, F - Na₂SO₄.

nitrates and sulphates show maximum changes in the absorbance of PGR-CDMEAB complex. It is expected that PGR can suitably be used with CDMEAB as colorimetric reagents in presence of cations like Na⁺ and anions like Cl⁻ ions.

Study of thorium and uranyl complexes of pyrogallol red (PGR) in absence and presence of CDMEAB :

The wavelengths of maximum absorption of PGR and its complexes with Th^{IV} and U^{VI} metal ions in absence and presence of CDMEAB in the pH range 2.5–7.0 are recorded in Table 2. For studying the nature of thorium and uranyl complexes in absence and presence of CDMEAB, the comparative absorption spectra of PGR have been plotted for Th^{IV} at pH 4.0 and in Fig. 3 and for U^{VI} at pH 7.0 in Fig. 4 respectively.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of Th^{IV} at pH 4.0, A - PGR-CDMEAB-Th^{IV} - (Ternary complex), B - PGR-Th^{IV} at (pH 4.0) - (Binary complex), C - [PGR-CDMEAB] - (Modified reagent) and D - PGR - (Reagent). Final conc. of PGR = 2.0 × 10⁻⁵ M, Final conc. of CDMEAB = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, Final conc. of Th^{IV} = 6.0 × 10⁻⁵ M.

Table 2. Absorbance maximum (nm) of PGR and its complexes in absence and presence of CDMEAB at different pH values

pH	2.5	3.0	3.5	4.0	4.5	5.0	5.5	6.0	6.5	7.0
PGR	480	480	480	510	510	510	550	560	560	560
PGR + CDMEAB	480	480	510	530	550	550	580	580	580	580
PGR + Th ^{IV}	470	540	550	550	550	550				
PGR + CDMEAB + Th ^{IV}	600	600	600	600	600	600	600	580	580	
PGR + U ^{VI}	470	470	470	560	560	570	570	570	570	580
PGR + CDMEAB + U ^{VI}	570	570	570	610	610	610	610	610	610	610

Study of binary and ternary complexes of thorium :

During complex formation with Th^{IV} ions in the pH range 3.5–5.0, the λ_{max} of PGR has been shifted to 550 nm. The λ_{max} of thorium complex has been observed at 470 nm at pH 2.5 and at 540 nm at pH 3.0. In the pH range 2.5–5.5 the maximum absorption of thorium complex in presence of CDMEAB has been found at 600 nm. The precipitation of thorium complex has occurred above pH 5.0 in absence of CDMEAB. However in presence of CDMEAB the precipitation of thorium complex has not taken place up to pH 6.5. Absorption spectra of thorium complex of PGR are shown by curve B in Fig. 3 showing the maximum absorbance at 550 nm. Absorption spectra of thorium complex of PGR in presence of five fold excess of CDMEAB represented by curve A, shows the λ_{max} at 600 nm with a considerable increase in absorbance and bathochromic shift of about 50 nm during complex formation.

Absorption spectrum of PGR in Fig. 3 is shown by curve D with the wavelength of maximum absorption at 510 nm. Curve C shows absorption spectra of PGR in

Fig. 4. Absorption spectra of U^{VI} at pH 7.0, A - PGR-CDMEAB- U^{VI} - (Ternary complex), B - PGR- U^{VI} at (pH 7.0) - (Binary complex), C - [PGR-CDMEAB] - (Modified reagent) and D - PGR - (Reagent). Final conc. of PGR = 2.0×10^{-5} M, Final conc. of CDMEAB = 1.0×10^{-4} M, Final conc. of U^{VI} = 6.0×10^{-5} M.

presence of five fold excess of CDMEAB with λ_{max} at 530 nm with considerable decrease in absorbance values. Bathochromic shifts with increase in absorbance values have been observed due to the formation of intense colored ternary complex which has proved the utility of CDMEAB for the sensitization of colored reactions used for spectrophotometric microdetermination of Th^{IV} .

Study of binary and ternary complexes of uranium :

The λ_{max} of the uranyl complex with PGR in absence and presence of CDMEAB are also recorded in Table 2. The λ_{max} of PGR recorded at 510 nm in the pH range 4.0–5.0 is shifted to 560 nm in the pH range 4.0–4.5 and to 570 nm in the pH range 5.0–6.5 with decrease in absorbance values during complex formation with U^{VI} ions. The λ_{max} of PGR recorded at 560 nm in the pH range 6.0–6.5 has been shifted to 570 nm during complexation with U^{VI} ions. However, in presence of CDMEAB, λ_{max} of uranyl complex in the pH range 2.5–3.5 has been recorded at 570 nm. Curve B in Fig. 4 indicates absorption spectra of uranyl complex of PGR which quite distinct and shows complexation with maximum absorption at 580 nm, whereas curve A is absorption spectra of uranyl complex of PGR in presence of five fold excess of CDMEAB shows λ_{max} at 610 nm with a bathochromic shift of about 30 nm.

Absorption spectrum of PGR in Fig. 4 is shown by curve D with the wavelength of maximum absorption at 560 nm. Curve C shows absorption spectra of PGR in presence of five fold excess of CDMEAB with λ_{max} at 580 nm with decrease in absorbance value. No bathochromic shift has been observed for uranium complex but the absorbance decreases due to the formation of binary complexes. However a bathochromic shift with λ_{max} at 610 nm has been observed. But the difference in absorbance values of ternary complex and the reagent blank is higher than the binary complex which resulted in increase in molar absorptivities of ternary complexes. This proves the utility of CDMEAB for the spectrophotometric microdetermination of U^{VI} .

Effect of pH :

In Figs. 5 and 6, curve A is a plot of variations of λ_{max} with the change in pH of PGR. Initially the λ_{max} of PGR remains constant at 480 nm in pH range 2.5–3.5, it again remains constant at 510 nm in the pH range 4.0–

Fig. 5. Variations in λ_{\max} with changes in the pH of : A - [PGR] - (Reagent), B - [PGR + CDMEAB] - (Modified reagent), C - [PGR + Th^{IV}] - (Binary complex) and D - [PGR + CDMEAB + Th^{IV}] - (Ternary complex).

5.0 and remains constant at 560 nm in pH range 5.5–7.0. Curve B is a plot of variations of λ_{\max} with change in pH of PGR in presence of CDMEAB. The λ_{\max} shifts from 480 to 550 nm in pH range 2.5–5.0 and remains constant at 580 nm in pH range 5.5–7.0.

Curve C in Figs. 5 and 6 represents the variation of λ_{\max} of PGR in absence of CDMEAB (binary complexes) for Th^{IV} and U^{VI} respectively. Initially for Th^{IV} the λ_{\max} shifts from 470 to 540 nm in the pH range 2.5–3.0 and remains constant at 550 nm in the pH range 3.5–5.0 above which precipitation has been observed. For U^{VI} the λ_{\max} remains constant at 470 nm in the pH range 2.5–3.5. It again remains constant at 570 nm in the pH range 5.0–6.5 and finally reaches to 580 nm at pH 7.0. The variations of λ_{\max} of PGR with pH in presence of CDMEAB (ternary complex) in the pH range 3.0–7.0 have been represented by curve D in Figs. 5 and 6 for Th^{IV} and U^{VI} respectively. In the Fig. 5, curve D shows constant λ_{\max} at 600 nm for the complex of Th^{IV} ions with PGR in presence of CDMEAB. However, in Fig. 6 indicates shift of λ_{\max} of the uranyl complex of PGR in presence of CDMEAB (ternary complex) from 570 to 610 nm in the pH range 3.0–7.0.

Fig. 6. Variations in λ_{\max} with changes in the pH of : A - [PGR] - (Reagent), B - [PGR + CDMEAB] - (Modified reagent), C - [PGR + U^{VI}] - (Binary complex) and D - [PGR + CDMEAB + U^{VI}] - (Ternary complex).

The variations of the absorbances with change in pH of thorium and uranyl complexes with PGR in presence of CDMEAB at their respective λ_{\max} have been represented by curve A and B in Fig. 7. Curve A shows the constant absorbance values of the ternary complex of tho-

Fig. 7. Variations in absorbance at the λ_{\max} with changes in the pH of : A - λ_{\max} 660 nm of [PGR-CDMEAB]-Th^{IV}, B - λ_{\max} 650 nm of [PGR-CDMEAB]-U^{VI}.

rium at λ_{\max} 660 nm in the pH range 3.0–5.0. Curve B indicates that absorbance of the ternary complex of uranium at the λ_{\max} 650 nm first increases in the pH range 3.0–5.0 and then remains constant in pH range 5.0–7.0. These optimum pH ranges of stability of constant absorbance of ternary complexes of thorium and uranium at the λ_{\max} of the complexes have been also given in Table 2.

Composition of complexes :

The spectral studies have shown the formation of only one complex with thorium and uranyl ions. The composition of the complexes has been studied by Job's method²⁸ of continuous variations. Figs. 8 and 9 show the composition of binary complexes of Th^{IV} at pH 4.0 at 560 nm and ternary complexes at pH 4.0 at 660 nm respectively.

Fig. 8. Curves of Job's method of binary complex shows composition of Th^{IV} : PGR as 1 : 2 at pH 4.0 and λ_{\max} 560 nm.

The results obtained were further confirmed by mole ratio method as shown in Figs. 12 and 13 at their respective pH and wavelength of study.

Similar studies have been carried out for the determination of composition of U^{VI} complexes in absence and presence of CDMEAB by Job's method as shown in Figs. 10 and 11. Further confirmation of the composition have been carried out by mole ratio method as shown in Figs. 14 and 15 in absence and presence of CDMEAB respectively. The results are thus obtained are given in Table 2.

In absence of CDMEAB the composition of the complexes has been observed to be 1 : 2 as M : PGR for both

Fig. 9. Curves of Job's method of ternary complex shows composition of Th^{IV} : PGR : CEMEAB as 1 : 2 : 4 at pH 4.0 and λ_{\max} 660 nm.

Fig. 10. Curves of Job's method of binary complex shows composition of U^{VI} : PGR : as 1 : 2 at pH 6.5 and λ_{\max} 620 nm.

thorium and uranyl complexes. No change in the composition of the complexes has been seen in presence of CDMEAB. As PGR exist as PGR(CDMEAB)₂ at the pH of study, the composition of the complexes in presence of five fold excess of CDMEAB may be tentatively represented as M : PGR : CDMEAB as 1 : 2 : 4 for both thorium and uranyl complexes.

Stability constants of the complexes :

The stability constant values for thorium and uranyl

Fig. 11. Curves of Job's method of ternary complex shows composition of U^{VI} : PGR : CDMEAB as 1 : 2 : 4 at pH 7.0 and λ_{max} 650 nm.

Fig. 12. Curves of mole ratio method of binary complex shows composition of Th^{IV} : PGR as 1 : 2 at pH 4.0 and λ_{max} 560 nm.

Fig. 13. Curves of mole ratio method of ternary complex shows composition of Th^{IV} : PGR : CDMEAB as 1 : 2 : 4 at pH 4.0 and λ_{max} 660 nm.

Fig. 14. Curves of mole ratio method of binary complex shows composition of U^{VI} : PGR as 1 : 2 at pH 6.5 and λ_{max} 620 nm.

complexes of PGR in absence and presence of CDMEAB have been calculated from the curves of Job's method²⁸ and mole ratio method and noted in Table 2. The values of the complexes of thorium and uranyl ions with PGR in presence of five fold excess of CDMEAB have been considerably increased. This is due to the stabilization of ternary complex in the surrounding atmosphere of cationic micelles of CDMEAB.

Considering the reaction of the complex formation between metals and reagent (omitting charges) for sys-

tems showing a composition 1 : 2, the formation of complexes may be expressed by the equation,

In absence of CDMEAB

And in presence of CDMEAB

K can be calculated from eq. (1),

Fig. 15. Curves of mole ratio method of ternary complex shows composition of U^{VI} : PGR : CDMEAB as 1 : 2 : 4 at pH 7.0 and λ_{max} 650 nm.

$$K = \frac{x}{(a-x)(b-2x)^2} \quad (3)$$

Taking the two concentrations a_1 and a_2 , and b_1 and b_2 having the same absorbance value, i.e. the same value of x , we have

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-2x)^2} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-2x)^2} \quad (4)$$

Knowing the value of x from the above equation, K can be calculated by putting the value of x in eq. (3).

The above equations were used for the calculation of stability constant of the complexes in absence and presence of CDMEAB by Job's method and the values of $\log K$ obtained are shown in Table 3. Increase in the values of $\log K$ of ternary complexes clearly indicates that more stable complexes are formed in presence of CDMEAB.

Analytical applications of complexes :

Order of the addition of reagents and effect of temperature :

It is necessary to maintain the sequence of the addition of reactants in all the experiments. In the present work therefore CTMEAB was added to PGR solution. The solution was then kept for half an hour for the complete formation of so called PGR-CDMEAB complex or association. To this modified reagent solution, the metal ion solution was added for complexation. In presence of CDMEAB with five fold excess of PGR, the color intensity of the mixtures of reactants remains unaffected upto 60 °C.

Rate of color formation and stability of color at room temperature :

By measuring the absorbance at regular time interval, the stability of the color at room temperature was studied. It was observed that the maximum absorption was gain after 20 min of the addition of the reactants and no further change in absorbance have been observed. All the measurements were therefore carried out half an hour after preparing the mixtures.

Effect of reagent concentration :

Different amounts of $4.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ PGR solution were taken in each flask to which 20 ml of $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ CDMEAB solution was added. The volume of the solution was made to 50 ml. Absorbances were noted at 660 nm and at pH 4.0 for Th^{IV} ions and at 650 nm and at pH 7.0 for U^{VI} ions. It was observed that the amount of PGR required for a maximum color development must be three times than that of metal ions in presence of CDMEAB. However, in absence of CDMEAB the amount of PGR required for full color development must be atleast five times than that of the metal ions.

Table 3. Composition and $\log K$ values of thorium and uranyl chelates of PGR in absence and presence of CDMEAB

Metal ions	Study in		pH of study	Wavelength of study (nm)	Composition M : R or M : (R : S)	log K values by	
	A - Absence	B - Presence of CDMHAB				Job's method	Mole ratio method
Th^{IV}	A		4.0	560	1 : 2	8.70	8.68
Th^{IV}	B		4.0	660	1 : 2 : 4	8.90	8.87
U^{VI}	A		6.5	620	1 : 2	8.42	8.40
U^{VI}	B		7.0	650	1 : 2 : 4	9.39	9.37

Table 4. Photometric determination of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} metal ions with PGR in absence and presence of CDMEAB

Metal ions	Study with CDMEAB	Beer's law range (ppm)	Effective photometric range (ppm)	Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	Molar absorptivity
Th ^{IV}	A	0.46–3.71	1.39–3.48	0.0078	58200
Th ^{IV}	B	0.23–3.24	0.70–2.78	0.0062	61120
U ^{VI}	A	0.54–3.78	1.08–3.64	0.0099	30980
U ^{VI}	B	0.27–3.51	0.54–3.24	0.0056	52470

A - Absence and B - Presence of CDMEAB.

Confirmity to Beer's law and effective photometric ranges in absence and presence of CDMEAB :

The linearity between absorbance of the thorium and uranyl complexes of PGR in presence and absence of CDMEAB was verified by taking different metal ion concentrations. The final concentrations of PGR and CDMEAB used were $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ and $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ respectively. The volume of system was kept at 50 ml. The range adherence to Beer's law was found out. The ringbom plot of negative log of metal ion concentration versus % transmittance was obtained. From this effective range for the photometric determination was also calculated. Both these results are recorded in Table 4. The values obtained in presence of CDMEAB clearly indicate that metal ions can be detected at low concentration which is not possible in absence of CDMEAB and thus shows the utility of the ternary complexes in microdetermination of metal ions.

Sensitivity and molar absorptivities in the absence and presence of CDMEAB :

Molar absorptivities of thorium and uranyl complexes of PGR were determined by taking constant amount of metal ions with varying amount of five fold excess of CDMEAB. The sensitivities as per Sandell's definition were calculated in absence and presence of CDMEAB. Both the results for the complexes in absence and presence of CDMEAB are reported in Table 4. A considerable increase in sensitivities and molar absorptivities in presence of CDMEAB indicates the use of micelle forming cationic surfactant CDMEAB in sensitization of present color reactions.

Effect of foreign ions :

The study of effect of foreign ions was carried out by taking fixed amount of metal ions (81.0 μg of U^{VI} ions)

Table 5. Effect of foreign ions (cations and anions)

Interfering ions	Amount of interfering ions ($\mu\text{g}/50 \text{ ml}$)	Amount of U ^{VI} found ($\mu\text{g}/50 \text{ ml}$)	% Error
Mg ²⁺	720	81.59	+0.73
Mn ²⁺	200	81.56	+0.70
Cu ²⁺	400	82.30	+1.60
Pb ²⁺	600	80.75	-0.31
Ag ⁺	100	82.12	+1.39
In ³⁺	60	82.41	+0.74
Cl ⁻	1000	81.24	+0.29
S ²⁻	300	78.62	-2.94
NO ₃ ⁻	250	79.03	-2.43
SO ₄ ²⁻	80	82.66	+2.05

Amount of U^{VI} taken = 81.0 $\mu\text{g}/50 \text{ ml}$.

and determining their concentrations in the presence of number of interfering ions. The metal ions such as In³⁺ seriously interfered at all concentrations. The anions like NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻ also seriously interfered in the determination. The results obtained for the determination of uranyl ions are recorded in Table 5.

Procedure for microdetermination :

The pH of the metal ion solution containing about 40–140 μg of metal ions was adjusted to 4.0 for thorium ions and 7.0 for uranyl ions. Three fold excess of modified PGR solution of the same pH was added (The modified PGR solution was prepared by mixing PGR solution with five fold excess of CDMEAB solution and keeping for a minimum period of half an hour for full formation of PGR-CDMEAB complex). The volume was made upto 50 ml with distilled water of same pH. The mixture was then kept for about half an hour for maximum complexation and equilibration. Absorbances of these solutions were noted at 660 nm for thorium ions and 650 nm for uranyl ions respectively against the modified reagent hav-

Table 6. Microdetermination of individual metal ions

Metal ions	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g}/50\text{ ml}$)	Amount found ($\mu\text{g}/50\text{ ml}$)	Standard average deviation
Th ^{IV}	92.80	93.09	0.032
U ^{VI}	81.00	81.14	0.015

ing same concentration as a blank. Absorbances of these solutions were compared with calibration curve obtained under identical condition. Table 6 shows the results of spectrophotometric microdetermination of thorium and uranyl ions with PGR in presence of CDMEAB with the respective standard average deviations of 0.032 and 0.015.

Conclusion :

(i) The sensitization of PGR has taken place in presence of cationic CDMEAB ensuing into the formation of intense colored ternary complexes with bathochromic shift and increase in absorbance values at shifted wavelength resulted into the formation of heighten sensitivity and absorptivity in wider pH range.

(ii) The complexes between PGR and both the metals under study in the presence of CDMEAB are very stable and more sensitive in presence than in absence of surfactant.

(iii) This developed method for the microdetermination of Th^{IV} and U^{VI} is inexpensive involves the use of readily available reagents, allows rapid determination at low operating costs, and can be used in a simple laboratory pH meter and spectrophotometer.

(iv) The procedure showed simplicity, adequate sensitivity and having low limit of detection with comparatively very few interferences and more accurate than the other methods reported earlier.

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